

REPORT:

*A1.3.1: Review of methods for
measuring and simulating total volume
and dead volume*

Work package 1

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A1.3.1 M9	CMI with the support of IPQ, RISE, METU, FOG, DTI, INESC MN, and ALU-FR, will review methods for measuring and, if needed, simulating total volume and dead volume of microfluidic devices. A report will compile the findings of the review and will be shared to end-users and stakeholders.	CMI , IPQ, RISE, METU, FOG, DTI, INESC MN, ALU-FR

This report was written by:

Name	Institution	e-mail
Vania Silverio	INESC MN	<i>vsilverio@inesc-mn.pt</i>
Thomas Schrøder Daugbjerg	DTI	<i>tsda@dti.dk</i>
Elsa Batista	IPQ	<i>ebatista@ipq.pt</i>
Florestan Ogheard	FOG	<i>florestan.ogheard@gmail.com</i>
Oliver Bükér	RISE	<i>oliver.buker@ri.se</i>
Jan Geršl	CMI	<i>jgersl@cmi.cz</i>
Mariëlle Laimböck-Wouters	MaterialsXpertise	<i>info@materialsexpertise.com</i>
Alexis Paul Tzannis	HSE AG	<i>alexis.tzannis@hseag.com</i>
Bertrand Cinquin	ESPCI	<i>bertrand.cinquin@espci.fr</i>
Auke J. Kronemeijer	TNO	<i>auke.kronemeijer@tno.nl</i>

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1. Scope

This document provides a review of methods for measuring and simulating total volume and dead volume of microfluidic devices. The document presents definitions of total volume and dead volume, and presents a review of methods coming from existing literature and proposals for new methods to improve accuracy and representativeness of total and dead volume assessment.

2. Introduction

This section introduces the terms internal (total) volume, dead volume and residual volume, and it does so by briefly presenting their definitions as found in the literature.

2.1. Internal (total) volume

Internal volume, also referred to as total volume, is defined in the standard ISO 10991 Microfluidics – Vocabulary (ISO 10991). That standard defines internal volume as the total available volume comprised within a fluidic component, device, or system under normal atmospheric pressure.

More loosely, internal volume can be defined as the sum of all the channels, gaps and chambers within a microfluidic device.

2.2. Dead volume

Dead volume in microfluidics is defined in the standard ISO 10991 Microfluidics – Vocabulary, as the portion of the internal volume of a system that is not part of a continuous flow-path (ISO 10991).

In more mathematical terms, dead volume is a volume of region bounded by (enclosed in) a surface at which fluid velocity vectors are tangent to the surface (at each point of the surface). In other words, this region is inside an envelope through which no fluid passes (except processes like diffusion). It can be various circulation zones in cavities, blind channels, behind steps, etc.

Notice that the standard ISO 10991 Microfluidics – Vocabulary, also defines the term swept volume, as the portion the internal volume that is part of the flow path (ISO 10991). Here, the sum of the swept volume and dead volume equals the internal volume.

Practical understanding of the dead volume

Dead volume is treated as the set of geometries and interfaces that are poorly swept (low shear/low exchange) and therefore tend to retain liquid or trap/pin gas bubbles. Typical examples include corners, sudden expansions, port/connector cavities, valve seats, surface defects, and dead-end side pockets.

In many real-world setups, the practical dead volume is dominated less by the microchannels and more by the interfaces, i.e. connectors, ports, valves, and even short tubing runs—which can contribute disproportionately to unswept volume and therefore to performance limitations.

Motivation for the dead volume characterisation

The dead volume can have undesirable effects depending on functionality or application area:

1. Sample loss or concentration variations: Dead volume can trap precious reagents or components that never reach the functional region (sensing, reaction, separation). In low-volume chips this can be a relatively large fraction of the total sample.

2. Trapped fluid can slowly re-enter the main flow, causing long undefined compositional flows (i.e. concentration profiles), and smeared peaks in “analytical or sensor-based chips”.
3. Contamination or carry-over: when switching from sample A to sample B. Even though careful purging might result in residual A in dead zones that leach out over time, contaminating B. This is especially problematic in critical workflows (like reactive, analytical or clinical applications).
4. Undefined residence time distribution: this results in non-ideal behaviour deviating from the ideal ‘plug-flow’ behaviour. In case of reaction kinetics or yield prediction this is unwanted, especially when scaling is interesting and accuracy is required.
5. In case there is a large dead volume there will also be a slow response to changing flow rates, composition of the feed flow. Dead volume delays the overall response, and makes build-in feedback control loops less precise.
6. In a full setup (chip + tubing + connectors + valves), dead volume in connectors and manifolds can dominate the total internal volume. This needs to be taken into account in the design of some nice applications where the chip volume is small.
7. If cells grow into portions of microfluidic channels where no flow / perfusion will be generated, then this might be a risk for the cell biological performance and therefore relevance of the Organ-on-Chip readout.
8. Trapping of gas bubbles. Bubbles are a frequent root cause of assay failure and poor reproducibility because they can partially or fully block channels, trigger pressure spikes, and destabilize what would otherwise be steady flow.

Two main situations where dead volumes do not matter:

- When a large amount of product is available and so we do not care that we are losing some when establishing the “good” flows.
- We are going to work in a continuous way meaning that we do not care if it takes time to establish the good flow.

2.3. Residual volume

In large volume and flow field, the residual volume is the volume or quantity remaining in the measure after closing the drain valve that depends on the different liquids used and inner walls’ surface properties of the construction material of the measure (Malengo et al., 2024).

More loosely within the context of microfluidics, residual volume refers to the amount of fluid remaining in a system after pumping, mixing or transport processes, which cannot be fully removed. This residual volume usually accumulates in regions like valve seats, connection points, and microchannel corners, but can also stay in the channel due to the internal material wettability characteristics.

3. Internal (total) volume measurement

The EURAMET Calibration Guide No. 19 describes calibration of liquid volume measurements (Gaber et al., 2025). That calibration guide describes methods for volume measurement that are applicable to different types of volume instruments, for example volumetric flasks, graduated measuring cylinders, proving tanks, and pipettes. While these instruments and their volumes are typically larger than microfluidic devices, the principle of volume measurement from that calibration guide is still interesting for microfluidics. In fact, Batista et al. used that principle, i.e. the gravimetric method for volume measurement, to develop a measurement procedure for the internal volume of microfluidic devices (Batista et al., 2025).

EURAMET technical guide No. 4, developed under project 20NMR02 MFMET, also describes the method for determination of total volume and residual volume applied to microfluidic channels. (Batista et al. 2024)

3.1. The gravimetric method for volume measurement

The standard ISO 4787, the EURAMET Calibration Guide No. 19, EURAMET technical guide No. 4, and the publication by Batista et al. present the gravimetric method for volume measurement in greater detail (Batista et al., 2024, 2025; Gaber et al., 2025; ISO, 2021). Here the method is briefly presented, and the volume instrument under calibration is referred to as a device or microfluidic device.

The method weighs the device when empty and again when filled with a liquid, which is often distilled water or deionized water. The draining and drying procedures of the device are important to follow in order to ensure the accuracy of the method. The difference between the two weighing measurements expresses the mass of the liquid contained in the device. A conversion from mass to volume, at a reference temperature t_0 , is performed with the following equation (Batista et al., 2024, 2025; Gaber et al., 2025; ISO, 2021):

$$V_0 = (I_L - I_E) \times \frac{1}{\rho_W - \rho_A} \times \left(1 - \frac{\rho_A}{\rho_B}\right) \times [1 - \gamma(t - t_0)] \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

The parameters and variables of Equation 1 are:

V_0 – volume of the device at reference temperature t_0

I_L – weighing measurement of the device filled with liquid

I_E – weighing measurement of the empty device

ρ_W – density of the liquid

ρ_A – density of air

ρ_B – density of the reference weights of the balance used for the weighing measurements

γ – cubic thermal expansion coefficient of the material of the device

t – temperature of the device and liquid

t_0 – reference temperature

If the liquid is then removed from the channel of the chip by aspiration with a syringe or a pipette and the chip is weighted again one can obtain the **residual volume of that specific channel**.

The EURAMET Calibration Guide No. 19 recommends a formula for the calculation of the density of pure water, ρ_W , as a function of temperature (Gaber et al., 2025). It also recommends a formula for the calculation of the density of air, ρ_A , as a function of temperature, pressure, and air humidity (Gaber et al., 2025).

When using the gravimetric method for volume measurement for microfluidic devices, it is important to consider the precision of the balance and the difference of density between the liquid and air, $\rho_W - \rho_A$. Assuming the liquid used is pure water, the order of magnitude of the difference of density can be estimated to $\rho_W - \rho_A \approx 1 \text{ g/mL}$ (Gaber et al., 2025). For an estimate only considering the difference of density and the precision of the balance, a balance precision with order of magnitude of a *milligram* translates to volume measurement with *microlitre* resolution. Furthermore, a balance precision with order of magnitude of a *microgram* translates to volume measurement with *nanolitre* resolution. The

smallest resolvable volume might be greater than that estimate, because of uncertainty contributions from other parameters such as the densities and temperatures seen in Equation 1. Related to this, Batista et al. present realising internal volume measurements of microfluidic devices with near microlitre resolution (Batista et al., 2025). This method is also presented in the EURAMET technical guide No.4, dedicated to microfluidic channels (Batista et al., 2024).

3.2. Geometric (dimensional) method for volume measurement

From measured dimensions of microfluidic channels, the volume can be determined. For simple channel geometries, length of the channel can be measured by standard methods. Measurement of shape of the cross-sectional profile of the channels is then more challenging, especially in chips which are sealed. For transparent chips, optical methods can be used (Kaal et al., 2025), e.g. optical profilometry. For these methods, problems in measurement a channel depth can occur due to light propagation through multiple optical interfaces.

3.3. Flow-through method

Start with an empty (air-filled) microfluidic chip. Now connect the inlet of the microfluidic chip to a syringe pump using a tube and also connect the outlet to another tube. (The end of the tube at the outlet can be open to the atmosphere). Next, select a constant flow rate (not too low, not too high) at which it takes a few seconds to completely fill the microfluidic chip with water. Start the syringe pump and observe how the meniscus slowly travels through the air-filled tube and the liquid reaches the inlet port of the microfluidic chip. Now start the stopwatch and measure the time required for the liquid front to reach the outlet of the chip. The total volume of the microfluidic chip channels can simply be calculated based on the measured time and the known flow rate.

4. Dead volume measurement

A literature search for measurement of dead volume in microfluidics yielded results for related topics such as pipettes, volumetric apparatus, and the related term dead space. According to ISO 8655-2 which addresses piston-operated volumetric apparatus, dead volume is the amount of liquid that does not belong to the delivered volume, and which is contained during operation in aspiration or expelling tubes, valves and within the cylinder (ISO, 2022). In microfluidics there exists loading interfaces to dispense liquid into a microfluidic chip, and these may use the term dead volume to describe liquid left behind upon emptying, especially in the parts that are poorly swept (low shear/low exchange). (Hatipoğlu et al., 2018). Dead volume or dead space is also applicable to disposable syringes and the method for its determination can be found in ISO 7886-1 and 7886-2 (ISO, 2017, 2020).

To the best of our knowledge measurement of dead volume, as it is defined by ISO 10991 (ISO 10991), is novel research with limited literature. The subsections below present methods proposals for the measurement of dead volume, i.e. internal volume un-swept by flow path.

4.1. Volume estimated from device dimensions

This volume determination method is based on design schematics, design dimensions, and production tolerances for the microfluidic device, and divides the device into various internal components, i.e. channels, chambers, etc. For each component the theoretical volume is calculated based on dimensions. Given a flow path through the device, a qualified person will judge for each component if it belongs to swept volume or dead volume, and the person will calculate the dead volume by summing the volumes of its associated components. In future developments this idea could be used together with geometric measurements of the device dimensions.

One advantage of this idea is that it is simple and possible to execute without any physical measurement. A disadvantage of this method is that a person makes a judgement of what is swept volume and unswept volume, leading to uncertainties in the dead volume assessment. Another disadvantage is that this method uses the design dimensions of a device, rather than the device itself, which introduce a systematic error between the calculated volume and the real volume that is difficult to evaluate.

4.2. Filling the internal volume and purging the swept volume

This method is based on the liquid/gas replacement within the channels and chip components. The suggested procedure is as following:

- Weigh the empty device/chip.
- Fill the device directly with water. Here a pipette or vacuum can be used.
- In case of use of vacuum, then the vacuum is released, and the vacuum is used to suck in fluid 1 to fill the internal volume. Here, fluid 1 could be pure and degassed water, and fluid 1 could be provided from the bottom of a burette that is also open to atmosphere in the top. Ideally, this step should fill most of the internal volume of the device, and any unfilled internal volume should be negligible.
- The device is then connected to a flow generator capable of driving a flow of fluid 2. Here fluid 2 could be air or an inert gas like nitrogen. This connection should have an inlet and an outlet that together specify a flow path through the swept volume of the device.
- The flow of fluid 2 is activated, and the swept volume of the device is emptied of fluid 1. In the dead volume, which is un-swept and not emptied, fluid 1 should be left behind.
- The device is weighed again with the dead volume filled with fluid 1.
- The two weighing measurements are used in Equation 1 to calculate the volume of the dead volume. This approach might work well if fluid 1 is a liquid and fluid 2 is a gas.

One advantage of this method is that it uses the device itself, and it could characterise a device even if design dimensions were not available or inaccurate. A disadvantage is that there are several steps that all must work well to realise the proposed method: the application of vacuum, the filling of the internal volume, and the emptying of the swept volume. It may be that one or more steps are not completely effective or have other unforeseen challenges introducing additional uncertainties. Challenges with air bubbles staying in the device after the filling of the internal volume, could perhaps be mitigated by using isopropanol, degassed water, or adding a mild surfactant like soap.

4.3. Methods to monitor or visualise the dead volume

Several methods can be used to monitor or visualise the dead volume in a microfluidic device:

- Using tracers and monitor changes, i.e. inject a tracer of a certain known concentration at the inlet and monitor concentration as a function of time at the outlet. The effective volume that is displaced can be compared with the internal volume of the system. Difference is the dead volume. Internal volume can be determined from accurate filling of the system (can be risky due to potential air bubbles).
- Using fluorescence and monitor intensity changes, i.e. visualise how quickly different regions fill and clear when switching between dyed and undyed fluid.
- To use a manifold and monitor with a fluorescent molecule how long does it take for the fluorescence to arrive in the observatory part of the chip.

- To monitor how long it takes to rinse the chip, previously filled with a fluorescent fluid, to ensure that a second sample can be introduced with no pollution from the 1st one. This test could give recommendations of usage (tube length and diameter, rinsing time for a given flow rate/pressure, ...).

Several test protocols can be proposed based on the methods above or based on other methods using gas trapped in the dead volume zones:

Protocol 1: Bubble challenge test with retention and clearance scoring

Purpose: Directly measures the failure mode of interest: where bubbles pin, how long they persist, and what it takes to remove them. This is broadly applicable across chip materials.

Setup

Imaging: stereomicroscope or inverted microscope; record inlet region, junctions/expansions, chambers, and outlets.

Flow actuation: pressure controller or syringe pump (use the same actuation for all comparisons).

Working fluid: choose the real buffer/reagent if possible; for comparability, specify whether it is degassed.

Procedure (generic)

1. Prime the device with working fluid until no visible bubbles remain.
2. Introduce a controlled gas volume (air plug) upstream. Practical method: create a known-length air segment in a known-ID tube; gas volume = tube cross-section × plug length.
3. Run the device at a defined test condition (recommended: 2-3 levels of pressure or flow). Keep temperature constant.
4. Record time-lapse images/videos of known bubble-prone regions until bubbles are cleared or a maximum time is reached.
5. Optionally repeat with (a) degassed vs non-degassed liquid, and (b) with/without surfactant, to separate geometry-driven from wetting-driven pinning.

What to report (suggested metrics)

- Bubble retention fraction: retained gas volume / injected gas volume (or a proxy score if volume is hard to compute).
- Time-to-clear: time until no visible bubbles remain in defined regions (report median and worst-case).
- Critical clear condition: minimum pressure/flow that reliably clears bubbles within a target time.
- Pinning map: a simple annotated image showing recurring pinning sites.

Protocol 2: Tracer washout imaging to map low-kinetics pockets (dead-zone heatmap)

Purpose: Identifies regions that exchange slowly even without bubbles. These areas commonly coincide with bubble pinning sites (corners, expansions, connector cavities).

Procedure (generic)

1. Fill the chip with a fluorescent dye solution (or coloured dye for brightfield imaging).
2. Switch to clean solvent/buffer at constant flow/pressure (keep flow stable).
3. Record time-lapse images of the same fields of view used in the bubble test.

4. For each region (or pixel), compute intensity vs time and extract a clearance time (e.g., t50, t90, t99) or half-life.
5. Define a threshold (e.g., 1-5% of initial intensity) and compute the fraction of area/volume that remains above threshold after N residence times.

What to report (suggested metrics)

- Clearance time map (t90 or t99) as a heatmap over the geometry.
- Dead-zone fraction: area/volume remaining above threshold at a fixed time (or after a fixed number of residence times).
- Worst-case clearance time in predefined regions (inlet, junctions, ports).

Protocol 3: Outlet RTD (residence time distribution) to quantify hidden tails from dead zones and interfaces

Purpose: Provides a single, system-level readout that includes the chip and interconnects. Long tails in the outlet response are a hallmark of slowly exchanging regions.

Procedure (generic)

1. Run steady flow at a fixed volumetric flow rate Q .
2. Apply a sharp inlet stimulus: step or pulse of tracer (salt for conductivity, dye/fluor for optical detection).
3. Measure outlet concentration vs time (conductivity probe, inline optical detector, or image-based measurement).
4. Compute effective swept volume using mean residence time: $V_{\text{eff}} = Q \times t_{\text{mean}}$.
5. Quantify tailing with a simple metric such as (t99 - t50), or fit a two-compartment model (main flow + slow exchange compartment) to estimate a dead-zone fraction.

What to report (suggested metrics)

- Effective swept volume (V_{eff}) at defined Q .
- A tailing metric (e.g., time from 50% to 99% response) and its dependence on Q .
- If fitted: estimated slow-compartment (dead-zone) fraction and exchange time constant.

Protocol 4 (companion): Compliance / compressibility test for trapped gas detection

Purpose: Very sensitive to small, trapped gas volumes because gas is far more compressible than liquid. Best used as a companion diagnostic with imaging to localize the bubble.

Procedure (generic)

1. Fill and prime the system as usual.
2. Apply a known pressure step (pressure controller) or a known volume displacement (syringe) while monitoring pressure/flow response.
3. Compare the transient response (rise time, overshoot, relaxation) between a bubble-free baseline and the test state.
4. Infer effective compliance; an increase indicates trapped gas.

Notes for comparability across materials

Always state whether liquids were degassed, temperature, and surfactant use (all strongly affect bubble nucleation and pinning). Run at multiple flow/pressure levels to separate geometry-driven dead zones from wetting/contact-angle effects. Report which parts are included in the measurement: chip-only vs chip plus ports, fittings, tubing, valves.

Useful links

Below are several links to websites that discuss dead volume, sometimes called dead zones, in the context of microfluidics:

Residence Time Distribution (RTD) technical note (Coanda Research & Development). https://coanda.ca/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/5.07_RT_D_tech_note.pdf

Rotary valve carryover and dead volumes (AMF technical note). <https://amf.ch/technical-note/rotary-valve-carryover-and-dead-volumes/>

Microfluidic volume definitions (Fluigent expertise review). <https://www.fluigent.com/resources-support/expertise/expertise-reviews/what-is-microfluidics/microfluidic-volume-definitions/>

How to Make Leak-Free, Zero Dead Volume Microfluidic Connections (LabSmith app note). https://www.labsmith.com/applications/How_to_Make_Leak_Free_Zero_Dead_Volume_Microfluidic_Connections.pdf

Design Guidelines for Microfluidic Side Connect (Enabling Micro/Nano Technologies). <https://enablingmnt.com/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/Design-Guidelines-for-Microfluidic-Side-Connect-version-1.0-1.pdf>

5. Residual volume measurement of a microfluidic channel

The **residual volume** of a microfluidic channel can be determined once its internal (total) volume has been measured. After filling and weighing the chip to obtain the total volume of the chosen microfluidic channel, the liquid inside the channel is removed—typically by aspiration using a syringe or a pipette. The chip is then weighed again. The difference between the two measurements corresponds to the residual volume remaining in the channel, which can be calculated using Equation 1. This is adapted from annex C of ISO 7886-1 (ISO, 2017).

6. Internal Volume Simulation

The **internal volume** of a microfluidic device refers to the sum of all fluidic pathways, chambers, and reservoirs. Simulating this involves computational and analytical approaches:

- **Geometric Modelling:** CAD software (e.g., AutoCAD, SolidWorks) is used to design the microchannels and chambers. The internal volume can then be calculated by integrating the cross-sectional area along the channel length.
- **Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD):** Tools like COMSOL Multiphysics or ANSYS Fluent allow precise modelling of fluid flow through complex geometries. By defining boundary conditions and material properties, the software can compute the volume occupied by fluid under steady-state or transient conditions.
- **Analytical Approximation:** For simpler channel geometries (rectangular, circular), volume can be estimated using formulas such as $V=A.L$, where A is the cross-sectional area and L is the channel length. This is often used for quick checks before detailed simulations.

7. Dead Volume Simulation

Dead volume refers to regions where fluid stagnates or is not effectively flushed, often leading to sample loss or contamination. Simulating dead volume requires more nuanced methods:

- **Flow Field Analysis:** CFD simulations can reveal velocity distributions inside the device. Areas with near-zero velocity vectors indicate dead zones.
- **Particle Tracking:** Virtual tracer particles can be introduced into the simulation to visualize flow paths. If particles remain trapped or circulate without exiting, those regions represent dead volume.
- **Residence Time Distribution (RTD):** By simulating the injection of a pulse of fluid, RTD analysis can identify regions with excessively long residence times, which correspond to dead volume.
- **Mesh Refinement Studies:** High-resolution meshing in CFD ensures that small pockets or corners are captured accurately, preventing underestimation of dead volume.

Practical considerations

- **Device Complexity:** The more intricate the microfluidic design (e.g., with valves, mixers, or branching channels), the more critical CFD becomes compared to analytical methods.
- **Validation:** Simulations should be validated with experimental techniques such as dye injection or micro-PIV (Particle Image Velocimetry) to confirm predicted dead zones.
- **Optimization:** Once dead volumes are identified, design modifications (rounded corners, tapered channels, or optimized junctions) can minimize them.

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